

Supplementary material: Micromagnet-free operation of electron spin qubits in Si/Si_{1-x}Ge_x vertical double quantum dots

Abhikbrata Sarkar¹ and Daniel Loss^{1,2,3,4}

¹Department of Physics, University of Basel, Klingelbergstrasse 82, 4056 Basel, Switzerland

²Physics Department, King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals, 31261, Dhahran, Saudi Arabia

³Center for Advanced Quantum Computing, KFUPM, Dhahran, Saudi Arabia

⁴RDIA Chair in Quantum Computing

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Geometry-dependency: valley splitting, shear strain and electrical tunability in the vertical DQD

FIG. S1. **Simulated shear strain in the DQD due to the metal gate electrodes atop the Si/Si_{1-x}Ge_x heterostructure.** a) The xz -map of the $\varepsilon_{xy}(x, y, z)$ shear strain tensor component in the simulated DQD device. b) Similarly, the xy -map of $\varepsilon_{xy}(x, y, z)$ in the DQD under plunger gate P_1 . The Si/Si_{1-x}Ge_x/Si ($x=0.033$ here) layers are indicated in c). The DQD centered at point (390, 410, 0) nm spans the following range: $x \in [370, 410]$ nm, $y \in [390, 430]$ nm, $z \in [-6.25, 6.25]$ nm.

3D finite element method (FEM) simulations of the strain distribution at 0.1 K are performed using the Structural Mechanics module in COMSOL Multiphysics. The metal gate electrodes are modeled as stress-inducing layers on top of the Si/Si_{1-x}Ge_x heterostructure, and the resulting strain tensor is evaluated throughout the DQD region (Fig. S1). Standard material parameters for Si and Si_{1-x}Ge_x from literature have been used [1, 2]. Few of the relevant Si_{1-x}Ge_x parameters are listed in Tab. S1.

The dominant contribution to the large valley splitting originates from coherent interference of intervalley coupling at the two Si/SiGe interfaces defining the vertical double well. We first examine the dependence of the valley splitting on the barrier height, set by the Ge

parameters	values
lattice constant, a_l	$(5.43 + 0.20x + 0.03x^2) \times 10^{-10}$ m
density, ρ	$(2.3 + 3.5x - 0.5x^2) \times 10^3$ g cm ⁻³
Young's modulus, E	$(130.2 - 28.1x) \times 10^9$ Pa
thermal expansion coeff., α	$(2.60 + 2.55x) \times 10^{-6}$ K ⁻¹
heat capacity, C_p	$\frac{19.6 + 2.9x}{72.6x + 28.1(1-x)} \times 10^3$ J Kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
band gap, E_g	$1.12 - 0.41x + 0.008x^2$ eV
Poisson's ratio, ν	$0.278 - 0.005x$
relative permittivity, ε_r	$11.7 + 4.5x$

TABLE S1. **Si_{1-x}Ge_x parameters as a function of Ge fraction x .** For $x=0$, these parameters correspond to Si. Note that the value of thermal conductivity K has been taken from the plot in Ref. [2] highlighting its nontrivial variation with x .

concentration x in the Si_{1-x}Ge_x barrier. Varying x from 1.1% to 5.5%, we find that for $V_b=15$ meV, corresponding to $x=3.3\%$ (Si_{0.967}Ge_{0.033}), the valley splitting is maximized (Fig. S2a). In the absence of shear strain, varying the barrier width a between 2 and 3 nm yields oscillations in the valley splitting ranging from 260 μ eV down to 25 μ eV. When realistic gate-induced shear strain is included, these oscillations are substantially modified, with the valley splitting varying between 275 μ eV and 90 μ eV (Fig. S2b). Furthermore, at finite plunger fields $|F_z| > 0$, the oscillations are suppressed and a uniformly large valley splitting of order 150 μ eV emerges (Fig. S2c). This behavior reflects the interference of interface-induced intervalley coupling contributions from the two barrier interfaces. Since $2k_0 \approx 9.5$ nm⁻¹, the relative phase of these contributions is sensitive to changes in the barrier width on the scale of a monolayer (~ 0.14 nm). Consistently, we find that the valley splitting exhibits peak-to-peak oscillations when a is varied by approximately 0.16 nm. Gate-induced strain breaks the symmetry between the two interfaces, modifying the relative weighting of their contributions and thereby elevating the minimum valley splitting to 90 μ eV. Importantly, while the valley splitting exhibits oscillations on the monolayer scale at zero plunger field, gate-induced strain in realistic devices and plunger field strongly suppress this sensitivity, yielding a robust lower bound ~ 150 μ eV that is insensitive to atomic scale variations in barrier thickness. We also examine the effect of varying the barrier height on the electrical tun-

FIG. S2. **Valley Splitting dependence on barrier height and width.** a) 2D map of the valley splitting E_v as a function of plunger voltage F_z and $\text{Si}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x$ barrier height V_b . $V_b=15$ ($x=3.3\%$) exhibits the largest valley splitting. b) Valley splitting E_v as a function of the barrier width a at $F_z=0$. The circles and solid fit line in black denote the results without strain; while triangular markers and solid fit line in purple show results with strain. The oscillation in the valley splitting can be fit to a period of 0.31 nm. c) 2D map of E_v as a function of F_z and barrier width a in the presence of gate-induced shear strain.

FIG. S3. **Electrical tunability with varying barrier height.** a) g factor as a function of plunger voltage F_z for different $\text{Si}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x$ barrier heights V_b (plot legends given in meV). b) EDSR Rabi frequency f_π as a function of F_z at different barrier heights V_b ; $\mathbf{B} \parallel \hat{x}, \mathbf{E}_{ac} \parallel \hat{z}$. c) f_π vs. F_z at different barrier heights V_b ; $\mathbf{B} \parallel \hat{x}, \mathbf{E}_{ac} \parallel \hat{x}$. The barrier width is $a=2.5$ nm.

ability of the electron spin qubit. With increasing barrier height, the slope of the g factor increases, while $V_b=15$ meV ($x=3.3\%$) produces the largest variation (Fig. S3a). As anticipated, the EDSR Rabi frequency for microwave drive via the plunger gate enhances with increasing maximum $\frac{\partial g}{\partial F_z}$ close to $F_z=0$ (Fig. S3b). EDSR with in-plane ac electric field ($\mathbf{E}_{ac} \parallel \hat{x}$) is the fastest for $V_b=15$, close to plunger voltage where $\frac{\partial g}{\partial F_z} \approx 0$ (Fig. S3).

The z-double well potential basis

The double well potential is given by,

$$V(\mathbf{r}) = V_{\text{DW}}(z) + \frac{m_t}{2} \left(\left[\frac{\hbar}{m_t L_x^2} \right]^2 x^2 + \left[\frac{\hbar}{m_t L_y^2} \right]^2 y^2 \right). \quad (1)$$

$e_n < V_b$, even:

The z -basis states are calculated by solving the following equation: $\left[-\frac{\hbar^2 \partial_z^2}{2m_t} + V_{\text{DW}} \right] \phi_n(z) = e_n \phi_n(z)$. The piecewise function describing the double well potential is as follows:

$$V_{\text{DW}}(z, a, L, V_b) = \begin{cases} V_0 & L + \frac{a}{2} \leq z < \infty \\ 0 & \frac{a}{2} < z < L + \frac{a}{2} \\ V_b & -\frac{a}{2} \leq z \leq \frac{a}{2} \\ 0 & -(L + \frac{a}{2}) < z < -\frac{a}{2} \\ V_0 & -\infty < z \leq -(L + \frac{a}{2}). \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Below, we provide the full form of the transcendental equation and basis solutions for even and odd bound ($e_n < V_b$) and unbound ($e_n > V_b$) states. Note that $\gamma = \sqrt{\frac{2mL^2V_b}{\hbar^2}}$, $r = \frac{a}{2L}$.

$$\gamma\pi\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}(1+r) = n\pi + \tan^{-1}\left[-F\frac{1+\frac{e_n}{F\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}}}{1-\frac{e_n F}{\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}}}\right],$$

$$\text{where, } F = \frac{\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\cosh\left(\gamma\sqrt{1-\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right) - \sqrt{\frac{V_b}{e_n}-1}\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\sinh\left(\gamma\sqrt{1-\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)}{\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\cosh\left(\gamma\sqrt{1-\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right) + \sqrt{\frac{V_b}{e_n}-1}\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\sinh\left(\gamma\sqrt{1-\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)}, \quad (3)$$

$$\phi_n(z) = \mathbf{N} \times \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right)}{e^{-\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi(1+r)}} e^{\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi z/L}, & -\infty < z \leq -L(1+r) \\ \mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(-\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(-\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right), & -L(1+r) < z < -Lr \\ \cosh\left(\gamma\sqrt{1-\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right), & -Lr \leq z \leq Lr \\ \mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right), & Lr < z < L(1+r) \\ \frac{\mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right)}{e^{-\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi(1+r)}} e^{-\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi z/L}, & -\infty < z \leq -L(1+r), \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$e_n < V_b$, odd:

$$\gamma\pi\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}(1+r) = n\pi + \tan^{-1}\left[-F\frac{1+\frac{e_n}{F\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}}}{1-\frac{e_n F}{\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}}}\right],$$

$$\text{where, } F = \frac{\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\sinh\left(\gamma\sqrt{1-\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right) - \sqrt{\frac{V_b}{e_n}-1}\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\cosh\left(\gamma\sqrt{1-\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)}{\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\sinh\left(\gamma\sqrt{1-\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right) + \sqrt{\frac{V_b}{e_n}-1}\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\cosh\left(\gamma\sqrt{1-\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)},$$

$$\phi_n(z) = \mathbf{N} \times \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right)}{e^{-\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi(1+r)}} e^{\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi z/L}, & -\infty < z \leq -L(1+r) \\ -\mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(-\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right) - \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(-\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right), & -L(1+r) < z < -Lr \\ \sinh\left(\gamma\sqrt{1-\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right), & -Lr \leq z \leq Lr \\ \mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right), & Lr < z < L(1+r) \\ \frac{\mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right)}{e^{-\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi(1+r)}} e^{-\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi z/L}, & -\infty < z \leq -L(1+r), \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$e_n > V_b$, even:

$$\gamma\pi\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}(1+r) = n\pi + \tan^{-1}\left[-F\frac{1+\frac{e_n}{F\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}}}{1-\frac{e_n F}{\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}}}\right],$$

$$\text{where, } F = \frac{\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}-1}\pi r\right) + \sqrt{1-\frac{V_b}{e_n}}\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}-1}\pi r\right)}{\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}-1}\pi r\right) - \sqrt{1-\frac{V_b}{e_n}}\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}-1}\pi r\right)}, \quad (6)$$

$$\phi_n(z) = \mathbf{N} \times \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right)}{e^{-\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi(1+r)}} e^{\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi z/L}, & -\infty < z \leq -L(1+r) \\ \mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(-\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(-\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right), & -L(1+r) < z < -Lr \\ \cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}-1}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right), & -Lr \leq z \leq Lr \\ \mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right), & Lr < z < L(1+r) \\ \frac{\mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right)}{e^{-\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi(1+r)}} e^{-\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi z/L}, & -\infty < z \leq -L(1+r), \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$e_n > V_b$, odd:

$$\gamma\pi\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}(1+r) = n\pi + \tan^{-1}\left[-F\frac{1+\frac{e_n}{F\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}}}{1-\frac{e_n F}{\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}}}\right],$$

$$\text{where, } F = \frac{\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}-1}\pi r\right) - \sqrt{1-\frac{V_b}{e_n}}\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}-1}\pi r\right)}{\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}-1}\pi r\right) + \sqrt{1-\frac{V_b}{e_n}}\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi r\right)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}-1}\pi r\right)},$$

$$\phi_n(z) = \mathbf{N} \times \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right)}{e^{-\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi(1+r)}} e^{\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi z/L}, & -\infty < z \leq -L(1+r) \\ -\mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(-\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right) - \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(-\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right), & -L(1+r) < z < -Lr \\ \sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}-1}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right), & -Lr \leq z \leq Lr \\ \mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi\frac{z}{L}\right), & Lr < z < L(1+r) \\ \frac{\mathbf{num}(F)\cos\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right) + \mathbf{den}(F)\sin\left(\gamma\sqrt{\frac{e_n}{V_b}}\pi(1+r)\right)}{e^{-\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi(1+r)}} e^{-\gamma V_b^{-1}\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}\pi z/L}, & -\infty < z \leq -L(1+r). \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The transcendental equation can be solved on a graph by plotting LHS and RHS and identifying the intersecting points to produce e_n solutions for each cases. The normalization coefficient N can be obtained by using $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\phi_n(z)|^2 dz = 1$. Also, $\mathbf{num}()$ and $\mathbf{den}()$ de-

note the numerator and denominator of the expression in parentheses, respectively. For this work, we approximate $V_0 \gg e_n$ (infinite outer boundary of the double

well), in which case $\frac{1+\frac{e_n}{F\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}}}{1-\frac{e_n F}{\sqrt{V_0^2-e_n^2}}} \approx 1$.

FIG. S4. **Schematic of the pulsing sequence of hopping between top and bottom Si dots.** The in-plane principle axis of the g tensor are denoted in blue (red) for the top (bottom) QD, with an angular difference ϕ between them. Each $(\tau_t + \tau_b)$ sequence of hopping back and forth generates 2ϕ net rotation of the spin. Hence after n such sequences, e.g. single qubit S gate ($\pi/2$ rotation) can be achieved if $2n\phi = \pi/2$.

The $x - y$ basis is described by the following set of equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_l(x) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^l l! L_x \sqrt{\pi}}} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2L_x^2}} H_l(x/L_x) \\ \phi_m(y) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^m m! L_y \sqrt{\pi}}} e^{-\frac{y^2}{2L_y^2}} H_m(y/L_y). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Hopping-based spin rotation mechanism

An anisotropic g tensor can be harnessed to realize single qubit rotations via a spin hopping (or shuttling) sequence between the top and the bottom dots of the DQD structure. As demonstrated in figure S4, the spin could be initialized in the top QD in the direction of the applied magnetic field $\mathbf{B} \parallel \mathbf{x}$. The spin is allowed to precess from $-\pi/2$ to $\pi/2$ about the principal g -tensor axis for τ_t time, followed by the spin hopping to the bottom QD. The spin then precesses from $-\pi/2$ to $\pi/2$ about the principal g -tensor axis of the bottom QD for τ_b time. When shuttled back to the top QD, the angular difference ϕ between the two g -tensor axes would produce a 2ϕ rotation of the original spin orientation $\parallel \mathbf{x}$. By repeating this pulsing sequence n times, a $\pi/2$ rotation of the spin about the z -axis, for example, can be achieved if $2n\phi = \pi/2$. The gate-time for this rotation is estimated as $T_g^{\pi/2} = \frac{n}{f_L}$, where $f_L = \frac{g\mu_B B}{h}$ is the Larmor frequency of the electron spin qubit ($f_L \simeq 2.8$ GHz for the electron spin at $|\mathbf{B}| = 100$ mT).

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- [1] F. Schäffler, *Semiconductor Science and Technology* **12**, 1515 (1997).
 [2] Ioffe Institute, “SiGe: Basic properties and material parameters,” <https://www.ioffe.ru/SVA/NSM/Semicond/SiGe/basic.html>.